

Job Rotation and Patient Waiting Time at Federal Medical Centers in Nigeria

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Abstract

An employee is moved from one position to another within an organization using the job rotation strategy to gain experience and pick up new abilities. Thus, the study aims to look at the relationship between job rotation and patient waiting time in the federal medical centre in Nigeria. A convenient sampling technique was used to select one (1) Federal Medical Centre from each of the six (6) geo-political zone in Nigeria. From the population of 6380 healthcare workers across the six (6) selected federal medical centres in the six geo-political, 376 public healthcare workers were used as the sample size for the study using Taro Yamane's (1967) formula. An online adapted questionnaire was used as the primary source of data. The online questionnaire was designed with the use of google form. The need for a questionnaire survey method is due to the nature of the study at hand. The questionnaire was administered via emails and WhatsApp messenger to the healthcare workers in the six (6) selected federal medical centres across the six geo-political zone in Nigeria. The study adopted the spearman rank correlation to report the relationship between job rotation and patient waiting time in federal medical centres in Nigeria. The result showed that there is no significant relationship between job rotation and patient waiting time in the federal medical centre in Nigeria. This study recommends that the management of federal medical centres in Nigeria should come up with an effective job rotation policy that would benefit both the employees and the employers.

Keywords: Job rotation, patient waiting time, organization

INTRODUCTION

Job rotation is a technique that involves the transfer of an employee from one job to another within an organization to gain experience and acquire new skills (Akinwale & Kuye, 2023). The aim of job rotation is to increase employee motivation, job satisfaction, and productivity (Kumar et al., 2023). The healthcare sector is not left out of this technique as it is adopted to increase staff efficiency and effectiveness. The Federal Medical Centre (FMC) is a tertiary health institution located in Nigeria, provides quality healthcare services to patients. The medical center is reputed for its comprehensive medical services, ranging from diagnostics to therapeutic services. However, the hospital faces significant challenges such as inadequate staff, long patient waiting time, and the need to provide quality medical care to patients. To address these challenges, the hospital management adopted job rotation as a technique to improve staff efficiency and patient waiting time. This paper discusses the relationship between job rotation and patient waiting time in the Federal Medical Centre in Nigeria.

Research Objective

The specific objective of this study is to find out if there is a relationship between Job rotation as training and development and patient waiting in the federal medical centres in Nigeria.

Literature Review

Job Rotation

Job rotation has been defined as a management strategy that involves moving employees from one job to another within the organization for a set period. The aim of job rotation is to improve employee productivity, job satisfaction, and the acquisition of new skills (Botti et al., 2021). The term "job rotation approach" is also used to refer to cross-training, which is the planned process of switching employees from one department to another. Notwithstanding the challenges faced by hospitals, job rotation has ultimately been determined to enhance coworker connections, advance knowledge, move skills, build a team, raise awareness, promote psychological health, reduce conflict, and increase job stability. (Idris & Wahyudi, 2021). An analysis of the job rotation approach in the nursing profession by Alfuqaha, et al. (2011) shows that the levels of job conflict, job satisfaction, job commitment, and job rotation are all very high. rotation of nursing positions seems required given that job rotation is favorably connected with both job commitment and job satisfaction. Moreover, work rotation, and job dedication are recognized as important determinants of job satisfaction among Jordanian nurses. Al-Sammarraie and Shaikhah (2021). Additionally, Ondiba, et al. (2021) examined the cross-functional job rotation on corporate financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya. The result showed that job rotation has a positive and significant effect on the financial performance. Ravikumar et al. (2020) argued that motivation and human factors play a mediating role in the performance of employees due to job rotation. This study supports the value of job rotation in the banking business, which helps employers foster stronger bonds with their staff members and get more efficient results. A policy of job rotation can give workers a sense of fresh air and a new environment while also helping the organization enhance staff talents to boost performance. so that it might give employees job pleasure or satisfaction (Arta et al., 2023). These studies demonstrate the role of job rotation in employee performance. However, we have very few studies on job rotation in 2023, and also do not demonstrate the role of job rotation in the performance of healthcare workers in the federal medical centres in Nigeria.

Patient-Waiting-Time

Excessive wait times for care and treatment can endanger lives and have a negative impact on the standard of care provided. To meet the rising demand for high-quality medical services, it is crucial to cut down on patient wait times. (Al-Zuheri et al., 2021; Sadi et al., 2021). According to Dorosti et al. (2020), the patients are never followed up with by the center for a later date, which might cause havoc in Out-Patient Departments (OPD), as a result of phone or in-person referrals. Second, unable to handle canceling or delaying an appointment in an emergency Thirdly, an office visit that takes longer than expected to complete causes chaos in the center. Usman et al., (2020) opined that patient wait times have an increasingly significant impact on a clinic's capacity to draw in new clients in a market where health care is competitively handled. So, health management should work to not just cut down on patient wait times but also invest in tools and initiatives that help patients make the most of their time when seeking medical care. Patients who felt their wait periods were long were much less likely to be happy with their care and hospital.

Methodology

A convenient sampling technique was used to select one (1) Federal Medical Centre from each of the six (6) geo-political zone in Nigeria. From the population of 6380 healthcare workers across the six (6) selected federal medical centres in the six geo-political, 376 public healthcare workers were used as the sample size for the study using Taro Yamane's (1967) formula. The justification for the use of Taro Yamane formula in this study is because the population is known and large which is enough condition for the use of the formula. An online adapted questionnaire was used as the primary source of data. The online questionnaire was designed with the use of Google Forms. The need for a questionnaire survey method is due to the nature of the study at hand. The questionnaire was administered via emails and WhatsApp messenger to the healthcare workers in the six (6) selected federal medical centres across the six geo-political zone in Nigeria. The study adopted the Spearman rank correlation to report the relationship between job rotation and patient waiting time in federal medical centres in Nigeria.

Findings

The study used a normality test to test if the data is normally distributed or not. Spearman rank correlation is used to examine the relationship between job rotation and patient waiting time in federal medical centres in Nigeria.

Table 1: Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnova			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
PT	.074	376	.000	.984	376	.000
JR	.206	376	.000	.904	376	.000

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Table 1 shows two test statistics, Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk. Kolmogorov-Smirnov is the data set that are above 100 (Barbosa et al., 2020) while Shapiro-Wilk on the hand are data set less than 100 (de Souza et al., 2023). Consequently, the study will focus or rely on the variables under Kolmogorov-Smirnov based on a large number of responses. Since the significant values of the variables are all less than the p-value of 0.05, it shows that the data set are non-parametric or not normally distributed. Hence, the study will adopt Spearman Rank Correlation (Santiago et al., 2020) and not Pearson correlation to determine if there is a relationship between job rotation and patient waiting time in the federal medical centre in Nigeria.

Table 2: Correlations

		JR	PT
Spearman's rho	JR	1.000	.037
	Correlation Coefficient	.	.472
	Sig. (2-tailed)	376	376
	N		
PT	Correlation Coefficient	.037	1.000
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.472	.
	N	376	376

Table 2 showed the correlation between job rotation and patient waiting time in the federal medical centres in Nigeria. The correlation table shows a weak positive and insignificant correlation between job rotation (JR) and patient waiting time (PT) with a correlation coefficient of 0.037 and an insignificant p-value of 0.472. Consequently, it has been shown that there is no relationship between job rotation and patient waiting time in the federal medical centre in Nigeria.

Discussions and Conclusion

It was discovered that job rotation (JR) has no significant relationship with the patient waiting time in federal medical centres in Nigeria. This result agrees with the work of Alfuqaha et al. (2022). Their result showed that nurses who never had job rotation experience were less motivated, more challenged to accept the idea of job rotation, less competitive, and felt that they would lose their friends if they rotated to other departments. Additionally, this statement was also supported by the work of Foroutan et al. (2021). They opined that rotated employees are expected to leave their conform zone will eventually cause them to experience various negative feelings including stress and anxiety for not having adequate contribution in their new department. Rotated employees often find it challenging to express their ideas in a new team and adjust to a new environment, new colleagues, and new conditions which can eventually generate numerous problems (Reddy, 2020). Similarly in this study, job rotation may not be effective in the healthcare system. A healthcare worker being rotated to another unit may find it difficult to adapt to the new environment thereby increasing the patient waiting time in the hospital.

Recommendation

This study recommends that the management of federal medical centres in Nigeria should come up with an effective job rotation policy that would benefit both the employees and the employers. Also, the management should ensure that these hospitals are equipped with enough staff so that the movement of one healthcare worker from one unit to another would not affect the services the unit where the healthcare has been moved from. Encourage cross-training and job sharing to ensure that staff members have a range of skills and knowledge, set clear objectives and timelines for job rotation assignments to ensure that they are meaningful and effective.

Provide support and resources for staff members who are taking on new roles or responsibilities and monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of job rotation programs regularly to make improvements.

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